

In the Greek original, published by Carl Müller in the *Fragmenta Historicorum Graecorum* the passage of the Peter's work is following:

“Καὶ τηνικαῦτα ἐν τοῖς ἐνδοτέρω τῶν βασιλείων πάντας τοὺς ἄλλους χωρίσας, καὶ ἀρκεσθεὶς τῇ παρουσίᾳ Ἀφφάρβα καὶ Ἀρχαπέτου καὶ Βαρσαβώρσου ὧν ὁ μὲν ἕτερος ὑπαρχος ἦν πραιτωρίων, ὁ δὲ τὴν τοῦ Συμίου εἶχεν ἀρχὴν” (Petrus Patricius, 2010, p. 189)

Translation by Katarzyna Maksymiuk:

“Then, deep within the palace, after he had separated all the others and been satisfied with the presence of Aphpharban and (*h*)*argbed* (Burz?)Shapur, of whom the one of the two was prefect of the praetorians and the other held the governorship of the royal secretary”